

European Structural Integrity Society (ESIS)
Karpenko Physico-Mechanical Institute
of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine
Ukrainian Society on Fracture Mechanics
Lviv Polytechnic National University

6th International Conference
“Fracture Mechanics of Materials
and Structural Integrity”

PROGRAMME

June 3–6, 2019

Lviv, Ukraine

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**A. Balitskii, D. Dosyn, L. Frankevych, B. Kindratskyi,
Ya. Khaburskyi, T. Lenkovskyi, V. Poznyakov,
I. Shtoyko, B. Stasyuk, V. Uchanin, O. Zynyuk**

MONDAY, JUNE 3

18:00	Registration and Welcome Reception Location: Premier Hotel Dnister; (6 Mateika Str., Lviv) Dnister restaurant
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TUESDAY, JUNE 4

8:30–9:00	Registration Location: Lviv Polytechnic National University (12 Bandera Str.), Main Building
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9:00–9:40	Opening Ceremony Location: Lviv Polytechnic National University Main Building, Assembly Hall
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9:40–10:40	Session: Fracture and Strength of Materials Location: Lviv Polytechnic National University Main Building, Assembly Hall
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9:40 **Development of investigations on fracture mechanics of materials and structural integrity: achievements and perspectives**

Volodymyr Panasyuk

Karpenko Physico-Mechanical Institute of NASU, Ukraine

10:00 **The mechanism for counteracting cracking of high-manganese steels with austenitic structure**

Leszek A. Dobrzanski

Medical and Dental Engineering Centre for Research, Design and Production, Science Centre ASKLEPIOS, Poland

10:20 **Fracture mechanics study of cementitious materials reinforced with carbon nanotubes and nanofibers**

Emmanuel E. Gdoutos¹, Maria S. Konsta-Gdoutos²

¹*Academy of Athens, Athens, Greece*

²*University of Texas at Arlington, Arlington, Texas, USA*

10:40–11:00

Coffee Break

Location: Lviv Polytechnic National University
Main Building, Room 231

11:00–13:00

Session: Fracture and Strength of Materials

Location: Lviv Polytechnic National University
Main Building, Assembly Hall

- 11:00 **Crack propagation sensitivity index of quasistatic and cyclic loaded engineering structures**
Laszlo Toth
TVE Engineering Ltd., Hungary
- 11:20 **To the problem of the subsurface defects detection: theory and experiment**
Zinoviy Nazarchuk, Leonid Muravsky,
Dozyslav Kuryliak
Karpenko Physico-Mechanical Institute of NASU, Ukraine
- 11:40 **Application of the theory of large deformation in uniaxial tension - compression**
Andrzej Kurek ¹, Justyna Koziarska ¹,
Tadeusz Łagoda ¹, Karolina Łagoda ²
¹ *Politechnika Opolska, Poland*
² *Politechnika Wroclawska, Poland*
- 12:00 **Electrodynamic treatment (EDT) of welded joints by electric current pulses as an effective method for regulation of their stressed-strain states**
Leonid Lobanov, Nikolai Pashchin
Paton Electric Welding Institute of NASU, Ukraine
- 12:20 **Influence of the inclusion shape and the constraints level on damage to the elementary cell**
Jaroslaw Galkiewicz
Kielce University of Technology, Poland
- 12:40 **Peculiarities of the crack initiation and propagation in different specimen types**
Eugene Kondryakov, Olexandr Panasenko,
Andriy Kravchyk, Valeriy Kharchenko
G.S. Pisarenko Institute for Problems of Strength of NASU, Ukraine

13:00–14:20	Lunch Location: Premier Hotel Dnister; (6 Mateika Str., Lviv) Dnister restaurant
14:20–16:00	Session: Fracture and Strength of Materials Location: Lviv Polytechnic National University Main Building, Room 226
14:20	Stress-strain analysis of thin-walled structures of complex geometrical shape and prediction of destructive loads Roman Kushnir, <u>Bogdan Drobenko</u> , Mykhaylo Marchuk <i>Pidstryhach Institute for Applied Problems of Mechanics and Mathematics of NASU, Ukraine</i>
14:40	Mixed mode (I+II, I+III) fatigue crack growth description in S355/P355NL1 steel <u>Grzegorz Lesiuk</u> ¹ , Dariusz Rozumek ² , Jose A.F.O. Correia ³ , Mieczysław Szata ⁴ , Abilio M.P. De Jesus ³ ¹ <i>Wroclaw University of Science and Technology, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Department of Mechanics, Materials Science and Engineering, Wrocław, Poland</i> ² <i>Department of Mechanics and Machine Design, Opole University of Technology, Poland</i> ³ <i>INEGI/Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto, Portugal</i> ⁴ <i>Wroclaw University of Science and Technology, Faculty of Technology and Natural Sciences, Legnica, Poland</i>
15:00	Numerical analyses of biomass reinforced composite bridging element <u>Róbert Beleznai</u> , Zoltán Siménfalvi, Gábor L. Szepesi <i>University of Miskolc, Hungary</i>
15:20	Influence of stress ratio on functional fatigue of pseudoelastic NiTi alloy <u>Volodymyr Iasnii</u> , Petro Yasniy <i>Terнопil National Ivan Pul'uj Technical University, Ukraine</i>

- 15:20 **Influence of the atmosphere corrosion on the fatigue life of welded T-joints treated by high frequency mechanical impact**
Vitalii Knysh, Sergii Solovei, Lyudmila Nyrkova,
Ilyia Klochkov, Sviatoslav Motrunich
Paton Electric Welding Institute of NASU, Ukraine

16:00–16:20 **Coffee Break**
Location: Lviv Polytechnic National University
Main Building, Room 231

16:20–18:20 **Session: Fracture and Strength of Materials**
Location: Lviv Polytechnic National University
Main Building, Room 226

- 16:20 **Determination of GTN parameters of SENT specimen during ductile fracture**
Yassine Chahboub¹, Szavai Szabolcs¹, Zoltan Bezi²
¹ *University of Miskolc, Hungary*
² *Bay Zoltan Institute, Hungary*

- 16:40 **Influence of a local distributions of stress and strain before tip of a crack at mechanisms of fracture of HARDOX-400 steel**
Ihor Dzioba, Robert Pała
Kielce University of Technology, Poland

- 17:00 **Effect of the structure on the mechanical properties and cracking resistance of welded joints of low-alloyed high-strength steels**
Olena Berdnikova, Valery Pozniakov,
Artemii Bernatskyi, Tetiana Alekseenko, Volodymyr Sydorets
Paton Electric Welding Institute of NASU, Ukraine

- 17:20 **Evolution of the mechanical fields and fracture process of S355JR steel**
Ihor Dzioba, Sebastian Lipiec
Kielce University of Technology, Poland

17:40 **Strength of welded joints made of high-strength steel with different welding parameters**

Ihor Dzioba, Tadeusz Pała

Kielce University of Technology, Poland

18:00 **Short crack problem in delayed fracture mechanics**

Yuri Lapusta¹, Olexandr Andreikiv², Nataliya Yadzhak²

¹ *French National Centre for Scientific Research,
University of Clermont Auvergne, France*

² *Ivan Franko National University of Lviv, Ukraine*

19:00

Excursion

WEDNESDAY, JUNE 5

9:00–10:40

Special session: Environmentally Assisted Cracking

Location: Lviv Polytechnic National University
Main Building, Room 226

- 9:00 **Main factors causing stress corrosion cracking & hydrogen-induced cracking. Gaping in our understanding**
Mimoun Elboujdaini
Integrated Mechanical Material Corrosion Services (IM2C), USA – Canada
- 9:20 **Specific effects of hydrogen concentration on resistance to fracture of ferrite-pearlitic pipeline steels**
Ihor Dmytrakh, Andriy Syrotyuk, Rostyslav Leshchak
Karpenko Physico-Mechanical Institute of NASU, Ukraine
- 9:40 **Assessment of in-service degradation of gas pipeline steel taking into account susceptibility to stress corrosion cracking**
Olha Zvirko¹, Giovanna Gabetta²,
Oleksandr Tsyurulnyk¹, Nataliia Kret¹
¹ *Karpenko Physico-Mechanical Institute of NASU, Ukraine,*
² *Consultant, Italy*
- 10:00 **The energy approach to the evaluation of hydrogen effect on the damage accumulation**
Yaroslav Ivanytskyi^{1,2}, Yevhen Kharchenko¹,
Oksana Hembara^{1,2}, Olha Chepil^{1,2},
Yaroslav Sapuzhak², Nazar Hembara²
¹ *Lviv Polytechnic National University, Ukraine*
² *Karpenko Physico-Mechanical Institute of NASU, Ukraine*
- 10:20 **Hydrogen assisted crack initiation and propagation in nickel-cobalt heat resistant superalloys**
Aleksander Balitskii
Karpenko Physico-Mechanical Institute of NASU, Ukraine

10:40–11:00	Coffee Break Location: Lviv Polytechnic National University Main Building, Room 231
11:00–12:20	Special session: Environmentally Assisted Cracking Location: Lviv Polytechnic National University Main Building, Room 226
11:00	Developmental strategy for environmentally assisted cracking resistance of copper containing 7xxx series M. Ajay Krishnan and <u>V.S. Raja</u> <i>Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, India</i>
11:20	Influence of the gas hydrates on the rate of corrosion of pipeline <u>Lubomyr Poberezhny</u> , Andrii Hrytsanchuk, H. Grytsyliak <i>Ivano-Frankivsk National Technical University of Oil and Gas, Ukraine</i>
11:40	Prediction of the residual lifetime of gas pipelines considering the effect of soil corrosion and material degradation <u>Ivan Shtoyko</u> ¹ , Jesus Toribio ² , Viktor Kharin ² , Myroslava Hredil ¹ ¹ <i>Karpenko Physico-Mechanical Institute of NASU, Ukraine</i> ² <i>Fracture & Structural Integrity Research Group (FSIRG), University of Salamanca, Spain</i>
12:00	Features of stress corrosion cracking of degraded gas pipeline steels <u>Hryhoriy Nykyforchyn</u> , Halyna Krechkovska, Oleksandra Student, Olha Zvirko <i>Karpenko Physico-Mechanical Institute of NASU, Ukraine</i>
12:20–13:00	ESIS TC10 Meeting Location: Lviv Polytechnic National University Main Building, Room 204

13:00–14:20	<p>Lunch Location: Premier Hotel Dnister; (6 Mateika Str., Lviv) Dnister restaurant</p>
11:00–12:20	<p>Special session: Non-Destructive Evaluation Location: Lviv Polytechnic National University Main Building, Room 226</p>

- 14:20 **Role and importance of NDE in nuclear power plant life extension**
 Peter Trampus
University of Dunaujvaros, Hungary
- 14:40 **Method of acoustic emission in delayed fracture mechanics of structural materials**
 Zinoviy Nazarchuk ¹, Olexander Andreykiv ²,
 Valentyn Skalskyy ¹, Denys Rudavskyy ¹
¹ *Karpenko Physico-Mechanical Institute of NASU, Ukraine*
² *Ivan Franko National University of Lviv, Ukraine*
- 15:00 **AE technology in continuous monitoring of high-temperature pipelines at heating power plants**
 Borys Paton ¹, Leonid Lobanov ¹,
 Anatoly Nedoseka ¹, Stanislav Nedoseka ¹,
 Mihail Yaremenko ¹, Janos Gereb ²,
 Yuri Gladyshev ³, Vadim Beshun ³,
 Alexandr Bychkov ³, Alexandr Gaidukevich ³
¹ *Paton Electric Welding Institute of NASU, Ukraine*
² *VD2, Hungary*
³ *SVP “Kievskii TPP” PJSC “Kievenergo”, Ukraine*
- 15:20 **Monitoring of the wear of aircraft transmission toothed wheels by the FAM-C and FDM-A methods**
Andrzej Gębura ¹, Sylwester Kłysz ^{1,2},
 Tomasz Tokarski ¹
¹ *Air Force Institute of Technology, Poland*
² *University of Warmia and Mazury, Technical Sciences Department, Poland*

- 15:40 **Development of electromagnetic NDT methods for structural integrity assessment**
Valentyn Uchanin, Orest Ostash
Karpenko Physico-Mechanical Institute of NASU, Ukraine

16:00–16:20

Coffee Break

Location: Lviv Polytechnic National University
Main Building, Room 231

16:20–18:20

Special session: Non-Destructive Evaluation

Location: Lviv Polytechnic National University
Main Building, Room 226

- 16:20 **The String Model: a new interpretation of the metallic structures and its connected physical phenomena**
Giuseppe Nardoni, Ward Rummel, Peter Trampus
Academia NDT International, Brescia, Italy
- 16:40 **Determination of residual stresses by laser shearography method**
Leonid Lobanov, Viktor Savitsky
Paton Electric Welding Institute of NASU, Ukraine
- 17:00 **Detection of cracks in ferrous steel structures: new innovative eddy current techniques**
Valentyn Uchanin¹, Giuseppe Nardoni²
¹ *Karpenko Physico-Mechanical Institute of NASU, Ukraine*
² *I&T Nardoni Institute, Italy*
- 17:20 **Analysis of rotary mechanism fault features on the base of the spectral structure for vibration stochastic recurrence**
Ihor Javorskyj^{1,2}, Roman Yuzefovych^{2,3}, Pavlo Semenov⁴, Pavlo Kurapov³
¹ *Karpenko Physico-Mechanical Institute of NASU, Ukraine*
² *UTP University of Science and Technology, Poland*
³ *Lviv Polytechnic National University, Ukraine*
⁴ *Odessa National Maritime University, Ukraine*

17:40 **The methodology of evaluation and monitoring of the fatigue fracture at macrocrack initiation stage**

Roman Chepil, Olena Stankevych, Orest Ostash,
Bohdan Klym

Karpenko Physico-Mechanical Institute of NASU, Ukraine

18:00 **Determination of components of transient resistance of underground pipeline**

Roman Dzhala¹, Vasyl' Dzhala¹, Roman Savula²,
Oleh Senyuk¹, Bohdan Verbenets'¹

¹ *Karpenko Physico-Mechanical Institute of NASU, Ukraine*

² *Public Joint-Stock Company "UKRTRANSGAZ" –
Affiliate "Lvivtransgaz", Ukraine*

19:00

Conference Dinner

THURSDAY, JUNE 6

9:00–11:00

Workshop on Applied Mechanics

Location: Lviv Polytechnic National University
Main Building, Room 226

- 9:00 **Research progress and prospect of laser hybrid manufacturing technology**
Jianhua Yao¹, Volodymyr Kovalenko^{1,2}
¹*Institute of Laser Advanced Manufacturing, Zhejiang University of Technology, China*
²*Laser Technology Research Institute, National Technical University of Ukraine*
- 9:20 **Features of the estimation of the influence of various factors on the integrity of the RPV reactor under the action of a melt of metals during a severe accident**
A.A. Kotliarenko, A.Yu. Cirkov, V.V. Kharchenko
G.S. Pisarenko Institute for Problems of Strength of NASU, Ukraine
- 9:40 **Effect of carbon nanotubes on the properties of ceramic coating prepared by sol-gel combined laser cladding**
Qunli Zhang, Zhongzhi Yao, Jianhua Yao
Institute of Laser Advanced Manufacturing, Zhejiang University of Technology, China
- 10:00 **Research on porous structure of the implant**
Chunyan Yao, Zhongli Zheng, Wei Zhang, Yunfeng Liu
Key Laboratory of Special Purpose Equipment and Advanced Manufacturing Technology, Ministry of Education, Zhejiang University of Technology, Hangzhou Zhejiang, China

10:20 **Surface morphology analysis and wettability of steel and glass modified with graphene oxide**

Barbara Nasiłowska¹, Klaudia Olkowicz²,
Aneta Bombalska¹

¹ *Institute of Optoelectronics, Military University of Technology, Poland*

² *Institute of Precision Mechanics, Poland*

10:40 **Effects of high-frequency vibration on the micro-structure and tensile property in laser cladding of SS316L alloy**

Zhehe Yao, Xiaowen Yu, Jianhua Yao

Institute of Laser Advanced Manufacturing, Zhejiang University of Technology, China

11:00–11:20

Coffee Break

Location: Lviv Polytechnic National University
Main Building, Room 231

11:20–13:20

Workshop on Applied Mechanics

Location: Lviv Polytechnic National University
Main Building, Room 226

11:20 **Influence of gas flow on oxidation of molten pool during laser remelting under open-air condition**

Gaolin Yang, Jianhua Yao, Zhengting Ye

Institute of Laser Advanced Manufacturing, Zhejiang University of Technology, China

11:40 **Advanced deposition characteristics of diamond-reinforced Cu matrix composite coating by supersonic laser deposition**

Lijuan Wu, Jianhua Yao, Bo Li, Weilin Wang,
Xuanjie Huang, Qunli Zhang

Institute of Laser Advanced Manufacturing, Zhejiang University of Technology, China

- 12:00 **Consideration of the effect of biaxial loading and short cracks on RPV steel fracture toughness**
V. G. Sidyachenko, A. A. Kotliarenko
G.S. Pisarenko Institute for Problems of Strength of NASU, Ukraine
- 12:20 **Study on laser cladding Fe-based wear resistant coating on inner wall**
Jianhua Yao¹, Zhongyao Cai¹, Zhijun Chen¹,
Volodymyr Kovalenko^{1,2}
¹*Institute of Laser Advanced Manufacturing, Zhejiang University of Technology, China*
²*Laser Technology Research Institute, National Technical University of Ukraine*
- 12:40 **Influence of pipeline steel texture on macro- and micromechanisms of its impact fracture**
Yevstakhiy Kryzhanivskyy¹,
Liubomyr Poberezhny¹, Pavlo Maruschak²,
Mykhailo Lyakh¹, Volodymyr Slobodyan¹,
Vasyl Zapukhliak¹
¹*Ivano-Frankivsk National Technical University of Oil and Gas, Ukraine*
²*Ternopil Ivan Pul'uj National Technical University, Ukraine*
- 13:00 **Role of in-service conditions in operational degradation of mechanical properties of portal cranes steel**
Oleksiy Nemchuk¹, Myroslava Hredil²,
Vitaliy Pustovoy¹, Oleksandr Nesterov¹
¹*Odessa National Maritime University, Ukraine*
²*Karpenko Physico-Mechanical Institute of NASU, Ukraine*

13:00–14:20

Lunch

Location: Premier Hotel Dnister;
(6 Mateika Str., Lviv) Dnister restaurant

14:20–16:20

Workshop on Applied Mechanics

Location: Lviv Polytechnic National University
Main Building, Room 226

- 14:20 **Microcrack under internal pressure at dislocation defect**
Mykola Stashchuk ¹, Nataliya Hembara ²,
Vitalii Kovalchuk ³
¹ *Karpenko Physico-Mechanical Institute of NASU, Ukraine*
² *Ukrainian Academy of Printing, Ukraine*
³ *Lviv branch of Dnipropetrovsk National University of Railway Transport named after Academician V. Lazaryan, Ukraine*
- 14:40 **Corrosion of drill pipes in high mineralized formation waters**
Igor Chudyk ¹, Lyubomyr Poberezhny ¹,
Andrii Hrytsanchuk ¹, Liubov Poberezhna ²
¹ *Ivano-Frankivsk National Technical University of Oil and Gas, Ukraine*
² *Ivano-Frankivsk National Medical University, Ukraine*
- 15:00 **Qualimetric analysis of pipelines with surface corrosion defects**
Roman Dzhala ¹, Volodymyr Yuzevych ¹,
Vitalii Lozovan ¹, Andriy Mytsyk ²,
Ruslan Skrynkovskyy ³,
Mykhailo Yasynskiy ⁴
¹ *Karpenko Physico-mechanical Institute of NASU, Ukraine*
² *Public Joint-Stock Company “UKRTRANSGAZ” – Affiliate “Lvivtransgaz”, Ukraine*
³ *Lviv University of Business and Law, Ukraine*
⁴ *Ukrainian Academy of Printing, Ukraine*

15:20 **Fracture behavior of dissimilar welding of Inconel 600**

Teresita Sánchez Cruz ¹, Sebastian Jaureguizahar ²,
Heriberto Granados Becerra ³,
Victor Hugo López Morelos ³, Orest Bilyy ¹,
Jorge González-Sánchez ¹

¹ *Centre for Corrosion Research of Autonomous University of Campeche, Mexico*

² *Materials Science and Technology Research Institute INTEMA, Argentina*

³ *Institute for Research in Metallurgy and Materials, UMSNH; San Nicolás University of Michoacana, Mexico*

15:40 **Effect of the application of an external magnetic field during the process of fusing welding in stainless steel duplex 2205 in the resistance to cracking by corrosion fatigue**

Alexandro De León, Jorge González-Sánchez,
Orest Bilyy

Centro de Investigación en Corrosión, CICORR-UAC, Mexico

16:00 **Requirements for hydrogen resistance of materials in CI engine toxic substances powered by biofuels**

Jacek Jaroslaw Elias ¹, Alexander Balitskii ²,
Tomasz Osipowicz ¹, Karol Franciszek Abramek ¹

¹ *West Pomeranian University of Technology in Szczecin, Poland*

² *Karpenko Physico-Mechanical Institute of NASU, Ukraine*

16:20

Closing Ceremony

Location: Lviv Polytechnic National University
Main Building, Room 226

